

Vasicine—An Alkaloid Present in *Adhatoda Vasica*, Nees.

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In the course of an investigation into the reasons for the immunity of timbers from insect and fungoid attacks which is at present being carried on at the Forest Research Institute, the active principle of *arusa* or *bakas* (*Adhatoda Vasica*, Nees) is being studied.

Some work had been done on this subject by previous workers.¹ In 1888 Hooper showed that the plant contained a white crystalline alkaloid of which he studied some properties such as the solubility and response to some of the alkaloidal reagents. Some salts were also prepared when a solution of the sulphate was found to possess a slight right-handed rotation. Bamber also studied the question and attributed the active principle to a volatile alkaloid, while Giacosa in 1895 was unable to detect any alkaloid in a sample which he examined. Hooper therefore re-examined further samples when he again found that they contained an alkaloid which he named *vasicine*. Boorsma in 1897 also demonstrated the presence of a solid alkaloid. He amplified Hooper's work and determined the melting point, which he found to be above 160°.

¹ Hooper, *Pharmaceutical Journal*, 7th April, 1888, quoted by Dymock, Warden and Hooper, "*Pharmacographia Indica*," Vol. III, pp. 80 *et seq.* Hooper, "*Adhatoda Vasica*" *Handbooks of Commercial Products, Imperial Institute Series, Indian Section*, No. 10, (1897).

Hooper's results have further been confirmed by the present investigation at Debra Dun, when a white crystalline alkaloid has been isolated. An alcoholic extract of the dried leaves was concentrated under reduced pressure till most of the alcohol had distilled off. Warm water was then added and the aqueous solution precipitated with the help of lead acetate. Excess of lead was removed from the filtrate with the help of sulphuretted hydrogen. After getting rid of the excess of sulphuretted hydrogen, ammonia was added and the alkaloid extracted with the aid of chloroform. On evaporating off the solvent, the crude alkaloid was left in the form of a brownish solid. This was purified by repeated crystallisation from a mixture of alcohol and ether.

Estimation of vasicine was carried out in the following manner. 10 gm. of the powdered leaves were thoroughly moistened with 2 c.c. ammonia and 3 c.c. chloroform. They were then put in a percolator with 30 c.c. of ammoniated chloroform (2 c.c. ammonia per 100 c.c.) The solution was taken off at the end of 2 hours and percolation repeated with fresh additions of about 20 c.c. ammoniated chloroform till the combined extract was about 100 c.c. This was then successively shaken out with 10 c.c., 5 c.c., and 2 c.c. normal sulphuric acid diluted with two to three times its volume of water. The acid extract was treated with ammonia and treated first with 15 c.c. and then with three additions of 10 c.c. of chloroform. The solid residue left from the evaporation of the chloroform extract was then titrated with standard acid, using litmus as indicator.

The alkaloid content which varied with the season was about .2 to .4 per cent. in the samples examined.

Vasicine.—The base crystallised in the form of needles, and melted (with decomposition) at 190°-191°C.

It did not lose weight when kept in vacuo over sulphuric acid for two days. When it was dried at 100°C, the substance became slightly discoloured but no water was given off. It dissolved with ease in chloroform, alcohol, methyl alcohol and acetone, and was only sparingly soluble in water, ether, and benzene. It was practically insoluble in petrol. Treatment with strong sulphuric, nitric and hydrochloric acids or with Erdmann's (sulphuric acid containing a trace of nitric acid), Buckingham's (sulphuric acid containing ammonium molybdate) and Marquis' (sulphuric acid containing formaldehyde) reagents did not produce any characteristic colour. Solutions of salts of the base yielded characteristic precipitates with the alkaloidal reagents. Mayer's reagent (mercury potassium iodide) produced a white curd which changed into a crystalline precipitate. Sonnenschein's reagent (phosphomolybdic acid) and Scheibler's reagent (phosphotungstic acid) also produced precipitates. Characteristic double chlorides with gold and with platinum were yielded. It formed an insoluble picrolonate and a picrate the latter crystallising as needles melting at 199° (with decomposition). Mercuric chloride yielded a white precipitate. Wagner's reagent (iodine in potassium iodide) produced a red precipitate.

Combustion analyses showed that the base possesses the empirical formula of $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$. (Found: C=70.1; H=6.5; N=14.7. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$ requires C=70.2; H=6.4; N=14.9 per cent).

The equivalent weight was found on titration to be 188. Vasicine forms a series of salts in which it behaves as a monacid base.

The molecular weight of the substance was determined by noting the rise in boiling point of alcohol and of benzene. (M.W.=163.2 in alcohol and 214 in benzene. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$ requires M.W.=188)

The base dissolved in chloroform or in alcohol was optically inactive. A solution of its sulphate was also found to be without any action on polarised light.

There does not seem to be any methoxyl group in it as negative results were obtained when it was examined by Perkin's modification of Zeisel's method, both with and without the addition of acetic anhydride.

Vasicine hydrochloride. The hydrochloride was prepared by passing hydrochloric acid gas to saturation into an alcoholic solution of the base, and then precipitating the salt with ether. Fine white needles were obtained on crystallising it from alcohol and ether. The crystals contained two molecules of water of crystallisation which were given up at 110° leaving the anhydrous salt which melted at 204° C. The salt was very soluble in alcohol and in water, sparingly so in ether. (Found: Cl=15.8. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$, HCl requires Cl=15.8 per cent).

Double Chloride of Vasicine and Gold. This came out as a curdy precipitate on adding gold chloride solution to an acidulated solution of vasicine chloride. On keeping rosettes of orange brown feathery plates were obtained. Purification was effected by crystallisation from acidulated water. The crystals were anhydrous as they did not lose any weight on being heated to 110° C and possessed the formula $BHAuCl_4$ (Found: Au=37.0; Cl=26.5. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$, $HAuCl_4$ requires Au=37.3; Cl=26.9 per cent).

Double Chloride of Vasicine and Platinum. This was prepared and purified in a similar way to the above. The crystals which were in the form of yellowish brown needles possessed the formula $B_2H_2PtCl_4$ (Found: Pt=24.2; Cl=26.6. $(C_{11}H_{12}N^+O)_2H_2PtCl$ requires Pt=24.8; Cl=27.1 per cent.).

Vasicine hydriodide. This salt is prepared by the addition of hydriodic acid to a suspension of vasicine in methyl alcohol. The crystals which came out on concentration were slightly yellow. Recrystallized from water they came out in fine white needles containing 2 molecules of water, but from dry methyl alcohol anhydrous crystals in the form of white needles were obtained which melted at 195°C. (Found: I=40·0 $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O$, HI requires I=40·2 per cent.)

Vasicine sulphate. Similarly on adding dilute sulphuric acid to a suspension of vasicine in water and concentrating the solution, needles of vasicine sulphate came out. Recrystallised from water it contains two molecules of water of crystallisation. (In the anhydrous salt. Found: $SO_4=20\cdot1$. $(C_{11}H_{12}N_2O)_2\cdot H_2SO_4$ requires $SO_4=20\cdot5$ per cent.)

Vasicine methiodide. Vasicine dissolved in methyl alcohol was heated on water-bath with excess of methyl iodide under reflux condenser for two hours and a half. The methiodide which came out on cooling was recrystallised from methyl alcohol. The white needles thus obtained contained no water of crystallisation, and melted at 187°C. (Found: I=38·4. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2O\cdot CH_3I$ requires I=38·5 per cent.)

Hydroxymethyl vasicine. Vasicine methiodide was treated with a slight excess of baryta water on the water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The base which partially separated out on cooling was repeatedly extracted with hot benzene. The extract was washed with a solution of sodium carbonate and finally dried with anhydrous sodium carbonate. The substance which crystallised out on concentration was purified by recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether. The prismatic crystals thus obtained were slightly brown in colour and melted at 100°C. Dried carefully at 100°C for three

hours they did not lose any weight. (Found: C=65.7; H=7.4; N=13.0. $C_{12}H_{18}N_2O_2$ requires C=65.5; H=7.3; N=12.7 per cent.).

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